

Analysis of Social Support, Customer Review Quality, Social Commerce Trust on E-Commerce Satisfaction Study Tokopedia in Indonesia

Aida Sari¹, Dwi Asri Siti Ambarwati², Nuzul Inas Nabila³

^{1,2,3} Lampung University

ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine how social support, customer review quality, social commerce trust, and e-commerce satisfaction are at Tokopedia Indonesia. The authors choose Tokopedia because Tokopedia is an e-commerce from Indonesia and is influential not only in Indonesia but in Southeast Asia. Tokopedia also supports Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises and individuals to develop their businesses by marketing their products online with the Government and other parties.

The method used for this research is quantitative. It was then analyzed using the PLS technique, factor analysis, and hypothesis testing. The unit of analysis in this study is the consumer from Tokopedia.

The data support hypothesis H1 that social support has a positive effect on social commerce trust, H2 supports the hypothesis that customer review quality has a positive influence on social commerce trust, as well as H3 supports the idea that social commerce trust has a positive effect on e-commerce satisfaction.

KEYWORDS: Customer review quality, e-commerce satisfaction, social support, social commerce trust.

INTRODUCTION

E-commerce is buying and selling goods or services and transmitting funds and data through electronic networks, especially the Internet (Laudon, 2017). Social commerce has gained popularity in both practice and research. This refers to “any commercial activity facilitated and carried out extensively by social media. Social commerce has become a popular place that offers a wealth of information about products and services contributed by marketers and consumer volunteers. ConsumerConsumerse-commerce and online shopping due to the time limitations of their tight daily schedules. Thus, online shopping has become a solution as it can save costs, travel time, and more manageable payment (Daroch et al., 2020). Consumers increasingly use social commerce as a source of product-related information and participate in social media activities such as customer reviews and recommendations. In other words, social commerce includes buying and selling on social media or facilitated by social media tools. For example, consumers may see product information their friends post on Facebook. A recent report (Global Web IndexIndex8) shows that 45% of consumers interact with product reviews during their buying. According to (Zhang, H.; Lu, Y.; Gupta et al., 2014), user participation and virtual experience significantly influence social commerce intentions on social media. Another type of social commerce phenomenon integrates social media into traditional e-commerce. In this context, consumers can share shopping-related information on social media through e-commerce sites.

According to (Zhang, P., 2012), social commerce comprises various aspects, including people, management, technology, and information. Social media platforms include generally available forms such as Facebook and specific social shopping communities (Olbrich, R., 2011). This social shopping community provides features such as recommendations, ratings, and consumer profiles. Consumers can make purchases by clicking on the links of participating e-commerce sites. Therefore, social shopping is a particular social media context of social commerce. Similarly, other studies have shown that social interaction involves several features, including social, commercial, and technological e-commerce. In addition, there is a growing understanding of the emerging phenomenon of colonial trade, especially its role in building consumer confidence and encouraging buying behavior. This research will examine social support, customer review quality, social commerce trust, and e-commerce satisfaction at Tokopedia Indonesia. The authors choose Tokopedia because Tokopedia e-commerce is from Indonesia and is influential in Indonesia and Southeast Asia. Tokopedia also supports Micro, Small, and Medium, Enterprises and individuals to develop their businesses by marketing their products online with the Government and other parties.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Social E-commerce includes buying and selling on social media or facilitated by social media tools. For example, consumers can see product information posted by their friends on Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, Whatsapp, Telegram, etc., and decide to buy the product. Social commerce is a new channel for consumers to acquire (Goh, Heng, 2013); (Hajli & Sims, 2015); (Pagani & Mirabella, Pagani, M., 2011). Consumers generate information that is helpful for consumer generalization purchase decisions. Social commerce companies interact with their customers and build relationships, which are essential for companies to achieve profits and improve their performance.

Social support is defined as motivation in social commerce activities. Social support is information that makes the subject believe they are. It can be shaped by exchanging resources (i.e., verbal and nonverbal messages) between two or more individuals. Social support has been identified as the main factor differentiating colonial trade from traditional trade—informational support comes from sharing product-related information or providing advice, referrals, and recommendations.

Consumers can obtain social support through social trading activities such as customer reviews from various social media. Social help or solid social support allows consumers to learn about products, services, or brands and increase their understanding of shopping-related issues, thereby increasing their subjective trust in social commerce. Social support is also essential in building trust because it helps consumers to adequately evaluate products through observing other people's product knowledge and buying experiences and overcoming perceptions of uncertainty and risk in the buying process.

From this perspective, social support can increase consumer confidence in social commerce through their psychological perceptions, thus forming social trading experience more robust social support in the social context of business. So, the first hypothesis is as follows;

H1: Social support is positively related to social commerce trust.

Customer Review Quality. Previous research has proposed that information quality influences individual satisfaction and technology adoption. In e-commerce, information comes from e-commerce vendors and is critical because it provides value to consumers and reduces the uncertainty associated with the shopping process. By contrast, in social commerce, information (i.e., product reviews) comes from other consumers. In a scenario like this, consumers may find reviews from other consumers to be of high quality if these reviews are relevant and valuable. So, with a higher level of customer review with quality, the social trading environment is more likely to be accepted and used by consumers, increasing their social trading trust (Xiaolin Lin, 2019). So the second hypothesis is as follows:

H2: Customer review quality is positively related to social commerce trust.

Social commerce. Trust or consumer trust in fellow consumers is essential when exchanging product-related information. With high social commerce trust, consumers perceive that e-commerce sites and integrated social media and social commerce feature work well and meet their requirements during the shopping process. According to (Xiaolin Lin, 2019), consumers view e-commerce as a comfortable environment for shopping and feeling satisfied (e-commerce satisfaction). Thus, they are more willing to make a purchase.

H3: Social commerce trust is positively related to e-commerce satisfaction.

RESEARCH MODEL

Figure 1. Research Model

METHODOLOGY AND DATA ANALYSIS

Research Population and Sample. The method used for this research is a quantitative approach involving parameter estimation, hypothesis testing, establishing confidence intervals, and the relationship between two or more properties (variables) for parameters with a particular known normal distribution. Then analyzed using the method, factor analysis, and hypothesis testing using Warp PLS 7.0. The unit of research in this study is the customer from Tokopedia in Indonesia. The population in this study is Tokopedia consumers. Due to limited time and information, the researchers only researched Tokopedia. Sampling was conducted using non-probability selection; each respondent has a population criterion that does not hahas a difference to become a sample. More precisely, this sampling method is convenience sampling; population members are selected based on the researcher’s judgment. The researcher selects respondents based on the knowledge and views of the researcher, who considers that a person who is a member of the population is worthy of being a sample in this study. The respondent 138 online consumers Tokopedia online Analysis **Techniques.** This study uses the wrap 7.0 Partial Least Square (PLS) method. (Hair, Joseph F; Hult, G. Tomas. M., Ringle, 2013) Suggest several steps to evaluate the model structurally; the first is by conducting a multicollinearity test, then by analyzing the relationships in the model and estimating the model's predictive ability.

RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Factor Analysis. At the beginning of this study, a factor analysis test was conducted. It can be seen that all research indicators (27 indicators) meet the validity test criteria; this is indicated by the factor load value, which has a Validity ≥ 0 .—after testing the validity, testing the reliability of the constructs used in the study. All instruments in this study are also reliable, with a ≥ 0.8 .

PLS Test Results

In this main study, re-testing was carried out for the accuracy and consistency of the data on 138 respondents who used Tokopedia in their purchases. Next, test the hypothesis. In this test, further data processing uses the PLS analysis method for testing hypotheses 1 to 3.

Partial Least Squares.

They are testing the study results using Partial Least Squares, testing hypotheses 1 to 3 using the WarpPLS 7.0 program. The results obtained from the general result can be seen in table 1; the model has a good fit, where the P value for the Average Path Coefficient (APC) and Average R- squared (ARS) is $p < 0.001$, which means less than <0.05 . Likewise, the resulting Average Variance Inflation Factor (AVIF) is 2,070, which means <5 . This shows no multicollinearity problem between independent (exogenous) variables. Several iterations for this model are done five times.

Table 1. General SEM Analysis Result

Model fit and quality indices.
Average path coefficient (APC)=0.536, P<0.001
Average R-squared (ARS)=0.603, P<0.001
Average adjusted R-squared (AARS)=0.598, P<0.001
Average block VIF (AVIF)=2.070
Average full collinearity VIF (AFVIF)=2.695
Tenenhaus GoF (GoF)=0.617
Sympson's paradox ratio (SPR)=1.000
R-squared contribution ratio (RSCR)=1.000
Statistical suppression ratio (SSR)=1.000
Nonlinear bivariate causality direction ratio (NLBCDR)=1.000
Outer model analysis algorithm: PLS regression
Default inner model analysis algorithm: Warp3
Multiple inner model analysis algorithms used? No
The resampling method used in the analysis: Stable
Number of data resamples used: 100

Number of cases (rows) in model data: 138
Number of latent variables in the model: 4
Number of indicators used in the model: 27
Number of iterations to obtain estimates: 5

Path Coefficient.

The path coefficient and p-values indicate that social support has a significant effect on social commerce trust with a P-Value value <0.001 and a path coefficient value of 0.215, customer review quality has a significant effect on social commerce trust with a P-Value <0.001 and a path coefficient value of 0.381, and social commerce trust is having a significant impact on e-commerce satisfaction with a P-value of 0.001 (<0.05) and a path coefficient value of 0.609. The results of the path coefficient with WarpPLS 7.0 are in the table below.

Table 2. Path Coefficient

	<i>Social Support</i>	<i>Customer Review Quality</i>	<i>Social Commerce Trust</i>	<i>E-Commerce Satisfaction</i>
<i>Social Commerce Trust</i>	0,215	0,381		
<i>E-Commerce Satisfaction</i>			0,609	

Table 3. P Value

	<i>Social Support</i>	<i>Customer Review Quality</i>	<i>Social Commerce Trust</i>	<i>E-Commerce Satisfaction</i>
<i>Social Commerce Trust</i>	<0.001	<0.001		
<i>E-Commerce Satisfaction</i>			<0.001	

Hypothesis Test Results

The research model uses 138 Tokopedia respondents based on the results of hypothesis testing using Wrap PLS 7.0 in the table below.

Table 7. Hypothesis Results Using Warp PLS 7.0 (n=138)

	HYPOTHESIS	P-Value	DESCRIPTION
H11	Social support has positively related to social commerce trust.	P<0.001	Data Supported H1
H2	Customer review quality has positively related to social commerce trust.	P<0.001	Data Supported H2
H3	Social commerce trust have positively related to e-commerce satisfaction	P<0.001	Data Supported H3

DISCUSSION

The data support hypothesis H1 that social support has a positive effect on social commerce trust; H2 supports the hypothesis that customer review quality positively influences social commerce trust; and H3 supports the idea that social commerce trust has a positive effect on e-commerce satisfaction.

This research at Tokopedia supports e-commerce satisfaction from the variable factors of social support, customer review quality, and social commerce trust. This research at Tokopedia Indonesia uses social support from Instagram, Facebook, and Twitter, uses review quality from consumers, and trust from consumers to achieve consumer satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

Tokopedia integrates Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter for social commerce sites. By clicking on social media links for specific products, consumers can provide product information on their Facebook pages and write their opinions. Consumers can view posted information and visit product pages on Tokopedia by clicking on posts.

This study shows that social support variables, customer review quality, and social commerce trust influence the factors that shape e-commerce satisfaction.

IMPLICATION DAN FURTHER RESEARCH

This research still has some limitations and shortcomings, so it requires improvements for future research. The following are some possible suggestions for Tokopedia companies or to be applied to further research, namely that further research is expected to be carried out by increasing the sample of the population who buys at Tokopedia and adding hypotheses for e-commerce satisfaction.

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